

Management of Concurrent Diseases in Backyard Poultry in Runjin Sambo Area Sokoto, Nigeria: A Case Report

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A client presented a dead hen to the Avian unit of the Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto after referral from Zonal Veterinary Clinic, Aliyu Jodi, Sokoto with complaints mortality, reduced feed intake and dullness in his small back yard poultry consisting of broilers, local chickens and guinea fowls. Ambulatory team was organized and the client's house was visited. Concurrent diseases including Newcastle disease, Fowl pox, tick infestation and heat stress were diagnosed, the flock was treated symptomatically. The results confirmed Newcastle disease, tick infestation and Fowl typhoid. It was concluded that problems encountered were as a result of poor management practices in the poultry house. There was recommendation of improving on the management practices in the farm and government should formulate policy that will make insurance and stock expansion more affordable.

Key words: Back yard poultry, concurrent infections, management problems, Sokoto, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture as an important sector of the Nigerian economy with high potentials for food security and poverty reduction, it provides direct employment for rural and urban dwellers and indirect employment for suppliers of products and services used to support poultry production and marketing activities (Adeyemo and Onikoyi, 2012). Poultry production in Nigeria is still facing challenges despite the fast-growing trade. The costs of labour, medication, veterinary services and fluctuating feed prices constitute substantial input costs in poultry production and pose a threat to the industry (Heise *et al.*, 2015). Poultry production mostly includes raising of broilers, layers, and cockerels as well as village poultry which consist of edible domestic birds including chickens, ducks, guinea fowls, geese, pigeons, turkeys and quails among others which are mostly raised under the free-range extensive husbandry systems especially in the

sub-urban and rural areas (Copland and Adlers, 2005). In African settings, village poultry production system has influenced human civilization in several aspects which include economic, nutritional and socio-cultural aspects of livelihoods of poor rural households (Mulugeta *et al.*, 2013). Poultry remains the most widespread of all livestock enterprises; it constitutes an important pillar of food security improvements as well as socio-cultural and economic developments in most countries (Alders, 2005; Dieye *et al.*, 2010).

Poultry products have assisted household food security by supplying high quality animal protein (meat and egg) used as food, petty cash derived from sales and create jobs for rural dwellers, it provides base for the socioeconomic advancement in the majority of developing countries and this has led to increased demand for poultry products especially broiler meat (Radfar *et al.*, 2012). Village poultry are also shared as gift among relatives and friends; they are also used as sacrifices during religious and cultural festivals (Adlers, 2005).

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The major diseases of poultry are Newcastle disease, Avian Influenza, Infectious Bursal disease, Pox, Coccidiosis, Colisepticemia and worm infestation (Ibitoye *et al.* 2013). Despite the enormous potentials the poultry industry possesses, it regularly suffers major limitations including diseases, poor husbandry, low egg production, poor chick quality, poor and low performing breeds, poor weight gain/feed conversion, feeding and management problems and lack of capital (Mahmud *et al.*, 2008; Muhammed *et al.*, 2010).

This is a case report on management of concurrent diseases as a result of poor management in a backyard poultry in Sokoto

CASE REPORT

History

On the 27th of February 2024, a client from Runjin Sambo Area Sokoto, presented a dead hen to the Avian unit of the Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto with complaints of high incidence of death in his flock of local chickens and guinea fowls, reduced feed intake and dullness. History further revealed that the client presented some dead birds to the Zonal Veterinary Clinic, Aliyu Jodi, Sokoto about a month earlier to help determine cause of death after which heat stress was diagnosed together with general poor management. The birds were about 78 in number (30 guinea fowls, 35 local chickens and 13 broilers of different age categories). They were managed semi intensively and fed with wheat and maize bran. They were treated with Oxytetracycline, Tylosin, Amoxicillin, Virucine[®] solution, Colimycin and liquid multivitamin but still the mortality persisted and it was referred to the Veterinary Teaching Hospital for further action. There was no history of vaccination in the Flock. The environmental temperature was 38°C. Ambulatory team was organized and the client's house was visited.

House visitation, physical examination and clinical findings

Upon house visitation, local chickens, broiler chickens and guinea fowls were met which were housed in different cages with no beddings, the local birds roamed about in the surrounding environment during the day time and were caged at night. They were of different age groups mixed up together. The surrounding environment was dirty without enough provision of shade, the feeding troughs were too big for the birds where they had to jump inside before they could access the feed (Plates 1 and 2). The water containers were dirty. The broilers were managed intensively. On physical examination of the birds the following were observed: Weakness, depression, torticollis, presence of ectoparasites, nodular

Plate 1: The surrounding environment

Plate 2: Inside one of the cages

Plate 3: Broiler chicken exhibiting torticollis

lesions on the comb, respiratory rales, panting and diarrhea (Plates 3-5).

Diagnosis

Differential diagnoses were:

- Newcastle Disease
- Infectious bronchitis
- Chronic respiratory disease
- Fowl cholera
- Heat stress
- Borelliosis
- Colibacillosis

Tentative diagnosis was:

Newcastle disease concurrent with fowl pox tick infestation and heat stress.

Action taken

Plate 4: Tick infestation in a local chicken

Plate 5: Vent pasted with greenish diarrhea and paresis of the legs

Plate 6: Blackish nodular lesions on the beak and wattle of a local chicken

- Blood samples were taken from three chickens to clinical pathology laboratory of Faculty of Veterinary Medicine UDUS for sera extraction and hemagglutination inhibition test for Newcastle disease virus.
- Tracheal swabs were taken to microbiology laboratory FVM, UDUS for bacterial culture, identification and antibiotic sensitivity test.
- Ectoparasite sample was submitted to parasitology laboratory FVM, UDUS for parasite identification.
- Post mortem examination was carried out on the presented carcass.

Plate 7: Periorbital swelling and congestion.

Plate 8: Ecchymotic hemorrhages in the trachea of ocular mucous membrane

Plate 9: Petechial hemorrhages in the proventriculus with mucosal lining sloughed off

- The birds were managed symptomatically pending outcome of laboratory results. Management
- Tyloxid[®] powder (Tylosine tartrate 100mg & Doxycycline hyclate 200mg) 1g/L of drinking water for 7 days.
- K.C Vite[®] multivitamin (Vit B1 25mg, Vit B2 1.5mg, Vit B3 50mg, Vit B6 5mg, Vit B12 50mg, Vit C 20mg, Vit D3 2000IU, Nicotinamide 15mg & Chlorine 25mg) 3mls/L of drinking water for 5 days.
- 0.6% permethrin powder by dusting to be repeated after 2 weeks.
- Levamisole solution (1% Levamisole) at 100mg/kg orally once.

RESULTS

Laboratory findings:

All samples were submitted on 27/02/2024

Heme-agglutination inhibition antibody titre for Newcastle disease virus was Log 2⁵ for all the three samples. *Antibody titre protective standard for birds against Newcastle disease is Log2⁴ (OIE 2012). Parasitology result revealed soft ticks *Argas spp* adults and larvae. For microbiology, bacterial culture yielded growth of *Salmonella spp* after 24 hours of incubation at 37°C.

Sensitive to:

- Ofloxacin
- Nitrofurantoin
- Gentamicin
- Levofloxacin

Resistant to:

- Amoxicillin
- Tetracycline
- Cotrimoxazole

Post Mortem Findings:

- Periorbital swelling and congested ocular mucous membrane (Plate 7).
- Ecchymotic hemorrhage in the trachea (Plate 8).
- Petechial hemorrhage in the proventriculus and sloughing off of the mucosal lining.

Confirmatory diagnosis: *Argas spp* infestation and Salmonellosis

On the 28/02/2024, the birds were still weak, dull, anorexic and respiratory rales were prominent, 7 birds died in the night and medication was continued. On the 29/02/2024, the birds were more active, feeding had improved and medication continued. 3 birds died.

On 02/03/2024, paralysis and diarrhea persisted.

On 05/03/2024, Medication was changed to Gendox® powder (100mg gentamicin sulphate, 50mg doxycycline hyclate) 1g/L of water × 5/7. Mortality was not recorded from 06/3/2024 but few chickens still manifested some nervous signs.

On 02/03/2024, the birds were active and feeding well

DISCUSSION

Poor management is a predisposing factor to concurrent diseases in poultry houses. Protective housing, ideal environmental temperature, good feeding, separation of different ages especially in broilers or exotic commercial birds and routine vaccination are basic practices that should be ensured. According to Abbassi *et al.*, (1999) in their survey on Marek's disease, mentioned that farmers who kept birds of different ages together experienced Marek's disease more due to repeated infection of the adult chickens, which served as carriers to the newly housed chicks in a contaminated environment. This shows that raising of different ages together can serve as a means of transferring infection by carriers to a different

age group category. Nnadi and George (2010) also reported cases of concurrent infection by endo and ectoparasites in village chickens in the sub-humid zones of South Eastern Nigeria due to poor management. Also Adedeji *et al.* (2016) reported concurrent and natural field outbreak of Chicken infectious anaemia and Infectious bursal disease in commercial poultry farm containing in 5 Weeks Old Pullets in Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria as a result of poor management.

Anosike *et al.* (2021), attributed high rate of disease and pest attack, lack of funds and loan to poultry farmers, lack of technical knowledge, high rate of mortality, high cost of poultry feed, supply of poor quality chicks, inadequate poultry extension services, and inadequate access to and high cost of veterinary services as causes of management problems faced by poultry farmers. The Possible solutions being intervention by veterinarians in order to curb losses due to diseases, technical know-how for improving production should be made available to poultry keepers through extension services. Reid *et al.* (2024) reported mixing of birds of different species especially with wild birds can be predisposing factors to so many diseases like Avian Influenza.

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that concurrent diseases encountered in the back yard poultry were as a result of poor management practices in the small back yard poultry.

RECOMMENDATION

The clinicians recommended that the owner should provide proper bedding for the birds and properly insulate the roofs of the cages to reduce heat. There should be routine deworming and vaccination of the birds when due. The cages and the environment should be fumigated and the equipment be disinfected. There should be maintenance of good hygiene. Birds of different species and breeds should be separated, sick birds should always be isolated from apparently healthy ones

Also, the clinicians recommends regular training of farmers on methods of disease prevention and control. Government should assist livestock farmers by formulating policy that will make insurance and stock expansion more affordable.

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